

NSS

Neutrosophic Sets and Systems

Neutrosophic Science International Association (NSIA)

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Diploma Of Best-Cited Articles of NSS journal

This certifies that

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For The Paper Entitled

Neutrosophic Shortest Path Problem

Which is one of 28 papers regarded the best that had got the highest citation among 504 papers that published in NSS journal as of 2013 till 2020

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8 Aug. 2020